

HISTORY OF THE INTEGRATIVE APPROACH

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ABSTRACT: The new generation of state educational standards of general secondary education is based on a competent approach, and in this connection, the practical solution to the problem of how to form the basic and subject-related competences of students is waiting for a practical solution.

KEY WORDS: Integration, competence, basic competence, technology, computer-based education, traditional teaching, cognitive, conceptual, interoecion, synectics, thinking.

INTRODUCTION

Adaptation of the country's education system to the processes of sustainable development and modernization, the formation of basic and scientific competences of students through the active application of innovative ideas and developments in the process of integrated educational technologies is of urgent importance today. For example, systematic measures are being implemented to form and further strengthen the modern material and technical base of educational institutions, and to use it rationally, including equipping them with high-performance educational laboratories, computer equipment and other information and communication.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND METHODOLOGY

Integration means joining some parts or elements together and becoming a whole. The word "integration" is derived from the Latin word "integratio" ("integr" - complete, whole, whole), "reconstruction, restoration, filling", "integration" - "mutual to develop in a connected way", "integrate" means "to combine into a whole, to make a whole" [11; p. 48]. The concept of "integration" has several definitions. In particular, N. Poddyakova [46; p. 17] describes integration as "a method of composing several subject materials on the basis of their natural subordination to the task and single purpose of the methodology."

J. Herbert was the first scientist who tried to prove the necessity of integration in the pedagogical process. It covers four stages of teaching: transparency, association, system and methodology. The first two stages were proposed by Herbart for acquiring knowledge, while the second one was aimed at creating a "bridge to mastering new knowledge" [3]. He stated that "intellectual ability" refers to the ability of a person to recover previous knowledge, which is compatible with current knowledge.

K.Ushinskiy proved the didactic importance of the connection between the subject and the event, which leads to significant changes in the content of teaching and education. In his book "Man as a Subject of Education" he separated the objective relationship between the subject and real-life events from various associative relationships. According to his theory, the idea of an interdisciplinary approach was reflected as part of the problem of systematization of general education. He paid special attention to the importance of strengthening the accumulated knowledge. The connection between concepts and their development in the system of general subjects helps to expand and master the knowledge of students, which at the end of learning turns into a complete worldview.

RESULTS

Although the term "integration" is relatively new, it has a long history in meaning and essence. In the universe, in society, in life and production, in education, that is, from the micro world to the macro world, integration is of great importance. Integration is a very broad concept. In particular, the necessity of the integration process in education in the formation of the scientific worldview of the young generation, their environmental and informational culture is noted by world scientists. Pedagogical research on the provision of interdisciplinarity, which is embodied as an independent research direction, has a pedagogical impact on the developing individual. special attention is paid to the educational importance of interdisciplinary communication. It is necessary to highlight the role of the teacher in the implementation of educational activities in the pedagogical conditions in which inter-disciplinary communication is ensured. Integrative approach - involves taking into account, relying on, combining and developing competencies from different disciplines. [29; p. 64].

DICUSSION

Integrated technological approaches serve to clarify the general description of all social processes and define their perspectives. In some sources, it is explained that the production technology is a whole stage defined by the period that includes the processes from the selection of raw materials to the delivery of a certain product to the consumer [19; p. 336]. But technological processes in social life and technologies in the educational process have integrative and differential features. During the research, it became known that the integrative features of educational technologies depend on several factors. The process of teaching technology in general secondary schools is based on the

principle of continuity in students' learning of the basics of science, the integration of pedagogical and information technologies in the organization and conduct of the educational process, as well as the educational, it was necessary to comprehensively analyze that it depends on spiritual, universal values.

CONCLUSION

Therefore, the issue of an integrative approach to the educational process has a certain generality. Because the integrative approach used in the educational process requires dividing the technologies into pedagogical and information-communication technologies. Although the directions of these integrated technologies are different, they also have common aspects that unite them. It is an important task to study the science of technology at school, to determine the optimal (effective) ways of using information and communication technologies, and to determine their specific criteria.

Summing up the ideas and examples mentioned above, today we can assume that the integrated studies approach depends on various aspects of its content. A better comprehension of the essence, goals and objectives of integrative approach in training and upbringing process makes the implementation much easier. It can be resulted in comprehensive knowledge and skills acquisition, the enthusiasm for personal development, gaining the ability to think systematically, to analyze one's behavior reasonably, and obtain new knowledge and skills. All these things prove the significance and positive influence of integrative learning in the pedagogical process.

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